

Ultrasonic Needle Beam Generation in Water Using a Complex-Amplitude-Encoded Polymer Trapped-Air Acoustic Mirror

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Abstract— This research presents a complex amplitude encoded reflective acoustic mirror that integrates super-unit phase encoding with a parabolic geometry to generate ultrasonic needle beams in water at a given focal distance. The mirror, fabricated in PLA with air trapped inside, combines phase-only modulation with geometric focusing, enabling extended depth of focus and controlled beam shaping for ultrasonic underwater imaging applications.

Keywords— acoustic metamaterials, complex amplitude encoding, parabolic mirror, ultrasonic needle beam, water acoustics.

I. INTRODUCTION

Extended depth-of-focus ultrasonic beams are critical for biomedical imaging, nondestructive testing, and underwater sensing. Recently, complex amplitude encoding metalenses (CAEM) have demonstrated the ability to generate arbitrary ultrasonic needle beams using super-unit phase decomposition [1]. Separately, broadband reflective focusing using parabolic mirrors has been modeled through impulse-response formulations treating the mirror as a distributed secondary source [2]. In this work, we merge these two concepts by embedding CAEM phase encoding into a reflective parabolic mirror operating in water. Furthermore, the mirror is realized with plastic, exploiting the so-called trapped-air concept to overcome low impedance mismatch between water and plastic, thus preserving the intended functionality [3]. The objective is to realize a compact, passive, single-sided reflective metasurface capable of generating uniform needle beam for sound manipulation.

II. METHODS

A. Complex Amplitude Encoding

The target transmission function is expressed as:

$$T(x, y) = A_0(x, y)e^{i\varphi_0(x, y)} \quad (1)$$

Here both amplitude $A_0(x, y)$ and phase $\varphi_0(x, y)$ are space varying

as shown in the Figure 1. Following the CAEM strategy, the complex amplitude is decomposed into two phase-only components:

$$A_0(x, y)e^{i\varphi_0(x, y)} = 1/2 A_{max} (e^{i\varphi_1(x, y)} + e^{i\varphi_2(x, y)}) \quad (2)$$

Here A_{max} is the maximum amplitude of A_0 and such as $\varphi_{1,2}(x, y) = \varphi_0 \pm \theta$ where $\theta(x, y) = \cos^{-1}[A_0(x, y)/A_{max}]$. These phase distributions are spatially interleaved using complementary binary masks within super-units, ensuring statistical blending and effective amplitude control [1].

Figure 1: Complex Amplitude Encoding (a) Original Amplitude $A_0(x, y)$; (b) Original Phase $\varphi_0(x, y)$; (c) Binary Mask (Complementary Mask) for super-units and, by combining all of them, the (d) Final Phase $\varphi(x, y)$

B. Reflective Parabolic Mirror Model

Unlike transmissive CAEM plates, our design embeds the encoded phase distribution onto a parabolic reflector. The reflected field is modeled using the impulse response method described for plane piston reflection [2].

$$h(\mathbf{r}, t) = \int \frac{\delta(t - R/c)}{2\pi R} dS \quad (3)$$

Here, $h(\mathbf{r}, t)$ denotes the impulse response at position \mathbf{r} and time t , R is the distance between the surface element dS and the observation point, c is the speed of sound, and $\delta(\cdot)$ is the propagation delay [2]. Each point on the mirror acts as a secondary source as shown in Fig.2, and the desired reflected pressure distribution is obtained via superposition of

appropriate phase delays, obtained by realizing different path-length between the mirror surface and the trapped air volume, according to the profile of Fig.1(d).

Figure 2: Schematic Diagram of the Parabolic Modulated Reflector

The geometric parabolic condition ensures equal optical path to the focal axis, while the encoded phase introduces additional spatial phase modulation to generate extended needle beam. In addition, a clever trapping of an air layer inside within the parabolic profile ensures the mirror to act as a rigid acoustic reflector in water [3].

III. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Results were obtained via FEM simulations in COMSOL using full-wave acoustic modeling. The acoustic field produced by the proposed device operating in water was analyzed for input planar pressure fields with frequencies from 100 kHz to 1 MHz. The results show a focus condition over an extended frequency range, fully agreeing with the results shown in [2]. On top of that, a uniform ultrasonic needle beam is generated along the optical axis, as illustrated in Figure 3, because of the additional coded phase delay [1]. Note that at the present stage, the needling behavior is simulating by modulating the pressure field to reflect the desired phase delay. The design also demonstrates suppression of sidelobe oscillations through super-unit phase blending, as shown in Figure 4, which improves beam quality and reduces unwanted acoustic interference. The beam length can be tuned by optimizing the distribution of focal positions in the complex amplitude encoding process. Compared to purely geometric focusing, this approach enables programmable beam shaping while maintaining a compact passive structure. The design supports both single and off-axis needle beams without requiring multiple transducers or active arrays. Full simulations including explicit phase encoding on the mirror surface will be addressed in the extended version of this work.

Figure 3: FEM of parabolic reflector (a) without and (b) with the complex amplitude encoded pressure. The white line is the reference cut baseline for Fig.4.

Figure 4: Line graph of Pressure field obtained at the cut-line using the different pressure field input, as per Fig.1.

IV. CONCLUSIONS

A hybrid reflective acoustic metasurface integrating complex amplitude encoding with a parabolic mirror geometry is proposed. Operating in water and fabricated in PLA exploiting the trapped-air concept, the structure enables programmable ultrasonic needle beam generation. This approach bridges transmissive acoustic metalenses and reflective focusing systems, opening pathways toward compact underwater imaging systems and single-sided broad-band pulse-echo applications. Future work includes experimental validation, ultra broadband optimization, and integration with single-element transducers for medical and underwater imaging.

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